

CLASSIFICATION OF TYPES OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN BUSINESS

Davlatov Nurbek Nugmonovich

is a researcher at Samarkand State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10867921>

Abstract. This article presents scientific-theoretical views on how companies' approach to social responsibility can help improve their reputation in society and customer relations.

Key words: social well-being, quality of life of residents, types of social responsibility of business, directions of social responsibility management

The social effectiveness of the development of modern economic systems, increasing the general level of social well-being of their activities directly depends on the quality of management of social responsibility of business, the level of substantiation of its priorities and the most important directions of implementation, development of methodological means of business development.

It is necessary to take into account the opinion of all interested parties when studying the impact of social responsibility of business as an actual way to improve the quality of life of the inhabitants of modern economic systems. Investors, shareholders, supervisory and regulatory bodies, suppliers and business partners, all employees and their associations, as well as mass media, public organizations, representatives of the local community, etc., influence all processes that take place in enterprises. We are convinced of the importance of taking into account the attention of all interested parties, because modern enterprises of various types of regions are under constant pressure from these interested parties, and therefore it can be argued that their actions and decisions are reflected in a successful business.

Management of social responsibility of business is a system of voluntary purposeful implementation of the interrelated functions of analysis, planning, organization, promotion, control and evaluation of the participation of a

business entity in the formation and implementation of charity programs. In accordance with the provisions of the law, the implementation of additional measures to increase the human potential of employees, improve the socio-cultural infrastructure and increase the environmental potential to a higher level than the norm, aimed at improving the quality of life of the population, increasing the social well-being of the population, increasing the welfare and image will increase the efficiency and value of the business entity. .

The main directions of social responsibility management of business entities are presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Directions of management of social responsibility of business in modern economy

According to the proposed definition, an important criterion for the management of social responsibility of business is the voluntariness of social support activities by companies and charitable projects of their employees. In

this sense, the structure of social responsibility of business does not include financing of programs and projects implemented in some regions of the modern Republic of Uzbekistan. This occurs, for example, on the "Voluntary-Compulsory Basis", when regional authorities force some regional business entities to allocate part of their net profits to the development of regional projects (for example, joint financing of regional top clubs in football, tennis or chess).

Accordingly, as shown in Figure 1, only excess funds for the reproduction of ecological potential implemented by economic entities on a voluntary basis can be included in the activity in the field of social responsibility of business in the modern economy. The same directions of development of the environmental sphere, which must be implemented within the framework of the proposed approach, in accordance with the requirements of the current environmental legislation, enterprises that carry out certain emissions into the atmosphere, hydrosphere or lithosphere . does not belong to the category of measures in the field of development of social responsibility of entrepreneurship.

It should be noted that the issue of classifying the types of social responsibility of business in the modern economy has not been sufficiently developed in the national literature. To fill this gap, we have developed this type of economic and management classification according to the most important ones. (Table 1).

Table 1

Classification of types of social responsibility of business

Classification marks	Types of social responsibility of business	It was	It happened
1. Subject of social responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - international corporations operating in industrial markets; - social responsibility of corporations; - social responsibility 	Including only enterprises and organizations in the constituent	Consideration of regional clusters as a special subject of business social responsibility

	<p>of regional companies of different production profiles;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- social responsibility of subjects of regional clusters;- social responsibility of small business.	entities	management
2. Object side of social responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- personalized social responsibility of business;- personal responsibility towards social groups that are not directly related to the development of the business entity;- social responsibility aimed at developing typical groups of labor resources of companies;- personalized social responsibility towards specific individuals.	Consideration of social responsibility objects only for special purposes (charity, ecology, etc.).	It is proposed to classify the management of social responsibility according to the degree of personalization of the recipients of social assistance.
3. Institutional nature of social responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- social responsibility of business regulated by federal laws;- social responsibility regulated by regional norms and institutions;- social responsibility of business entities regulated by norms and institutions of municipal significance;- social responsibility regulated by local norms of business entities;- non-institutionalized social responsibility.	Consideration of social responsibility in terms of compliance with various legal institutions	Division of social responsibility management into laws, local regulations of the company and non-institutional (based on the director's order)

<p>4. The nature of the interaction between the subjects of social responsibility and state bodies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - social responsibility of business entities, which is carried out without interaction with state bodies of the economy; - social responsibility implemented within the framework of tax benefits and other compensation mechanisms; - social responsibility of business implemented on the basis of public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms. 	<p>Research on social responsibility management is mainly in the interaction with different levels of governments</p>	<p>Types of social responsibility management are distinguished according to the nature of relations between business entities and state bodies.</p>
<p>Features of influence on increasing the efficiency of socio-economic development</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - regional business that has a direct positive socio-economic impact on the development of the region; - social responsibility of business, which is mostly indirect, including. image effect for regional development; - quasi-social responsibility of business entities. 	<p>the focus is mainly on the positive elements of social responsibility</p>	<p>Introduction of the concept of social responsibility of business</p>
<p>6. Integration of social responsibility mechanisms</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - individual social responsibility of business entities; - project or software complex responsibility of business entities. 	<p>In special literature, social responsibility is not classified according to the integration mechanisms of management.</p>	
<p>7. Temporary nature of implementation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - one-time social responsibility of regional business entities; 	<p>Traditionally, short-term and long-term social</p>	<p>Classification according to the frequency of implementation</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - periodic social responsibility; - social responsibility implemented continuously. 	responsibility programs are distinguished.	of social responsibility
--	--	--	--------------------------

As shown in Table 1, from a subjective point of view, it is proposed to distinguish social responsibility not only of individual companies, but also of regional industrial clusters, within which certain joint social development programs can be implemented. When implementing social responsibility programs, such business entities, as a rule, prefer to finance the activities of global companies that do not have a specific territorial localization [1].

From the point of view of classification by object, the share of non-personalized social responsibility of business in the economy is of great importance, which is not carried out by modern companies towards their employees and their families.[2] Within this classification feature, we have identified quasi-social responsibility of business entities, which is an activity that has formal characteristics of corporate social responsibility, but in practice has completely different goals, for example, canceling the social responsibility of business entities. assets of business entities, money laundering, etc.

It is also important to distinguish the types of social responsibility of companies in terms of their impact on the overall socio-economic development of the region (district, region, municipality).[3] Within this classification feature, we have identified quasi-social responsibility of business entities, which is an activity that has formal characteristics of corporate social responsibility, but in practice has completely different goals, for example, the cancellation of social responsibility of business entities. assets of business entities, money laundering, etc.

From the point of view of ensuring the progressiveness of economic development, it is also relevant to classify the types of social responsibility of

business according to the level of integration. All other things being equal, the complex responsibility of business entities is more effective, within which not only the collection of financial resources from various sources for the implementation of charitable and other socially important projects, but also positive synergy is realized. It can occur as a result of the joint use of management and organizational efforts of several subjects of entrepreneurial activity.[4]

In general, the classification of social responsibility of business in the modern economy makes it possible to personalize the mechanisms and methodological tools for managing some types and programs of social responsibility of business companies. All other things being equal, the most optimal is the institutionalization of companies at the level of local regulatory legal documents, using the mechanisms of public-private partnerships in the economy and social sphere, integrated, implemented continuously, to have a positive impact, both direct and indirect. will be directed.

References:

1. Abrams R. Entrepreneurship: A Real-World Approach. Redwood City: Planning Shop, 2015. P.89.
2. Юн Е.Л., Божук С.Г. Классификация инструментов реализации корпоративной социальной ответственности в виртуальной среде// Неделя науки СПбПУ. Материалы научной конференции с международным участием. Санкт-Петербургский политехнический университет Петра Великого, Институт промышленного менеджмента, экономики и торговли. 2016. С. 280-282.
3. Ускова Т.В. Социально-экономическое развитие территорий: проблемы эффективности региональной политики// Проблемы развития территории. 2016. № 2(82). С. 7-18.
4. Струк К.Ю., Медведникова Д.А., Божук С.Г. Влияние социальной ответственности организации на ее популярность у покупателей// Неделя науки СПбПУ. Материалы научной конференции с международным участием. Санкт-Петербургский политехнический университет Петра Великого, Институт промышленного менеджмента, экономики и торговли. 2016. С. 277-279.
5. Косякова И.В., Салькина А.Р. Развитие механизмов государственного частного партнёрства в России// Актуальные проблемы и тенденции

**SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN
MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY**
International scientific-online conference

развития современной экономики. Материалы международной научно-практической конференции. Самара. 2015. С. 154-157.